

A Review of General Introduction to Political Communication (Brian McNair)

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Abstract

The relationship between the media and the political process is a dialectical, involving action and reaction. Media reports and analysis of political activity, is a resource for political actors and their counselors. Media, or those who work in it, should be seen as an important political actor in themselves. They not only send messages to the public political organization, but they change the message through a variety of news-making process and interpretation. What politicians say is not necessarily what the media reported as politicians desire. In addition, the media made a statement about their own politics, whether in the form of comments, editorials, and interview questions. Media reports may have a significant impact on the wider political environment.

Keywords : Politic, Communication

Introduction

When Edmund Burke describes the birth of the media in the eighteenth century as the 'Fourth Estate' (the first three are executive, legislative and judicial), he recognizes the importance of the media for the health of liberal democracy. Media represents an independent source of knowledge, not only inform people about politics, but also protect them from abuse. To realize this the role of the media should be free from interference / political threat. As Scannell and Cardiff, 'struggle to establish an independent press, both as a source of information about the activities of the state, and as a forum for the formation and expression of public opinion, an important aspect of long battle as full representation in the system of democratic governance' (1991, p. 10). Freedom of the press was founded on the principle of independent economic organizations. The newspaper was originally a private commercial institutions that exist to make profits for their owners. They are sold as a commodity on the market, at first (because of their high cost) only for the wealthy elite. But as advanced literacy throughout the capitalist world in the nineteenth century, and developed the production printing technology, the newspaper down in price and become more widely available. Print media to be the beginning of the media. At the beginning of the twentieth century mass media such as News of the World and the Daily Mail

sold millions of copies. As private institutions, the British press has traditionally been relatively free from interference in their activities with one of the other three. After emerging from the oppression and censorship of the feudal state, freedom of the press to pursue the story is always seen as central to the democratic process. Meanwhile, the Government often falls out with the elements of the press, has been restricted from the imposition of regulatory laws that can be interpreted as 'political censorship'. Restrictions on freedom of the press was restricted to issues of 'national security', such as reportage official secrets, and several ethics violations, including defamation. Obstacles in the subject area of coverage is a matter of debate, and new restrictions designed to protect the privacy of individuals is still very much on the agenda in the UK.

Broadcasting Environment

While the press since its inception has functioned as essentially set a capitalist company, broadcasting has taken a variety of forms of organization. In the US, radio and television - as the press - to be commercially developed, funded by advertising revenue. In Soviet Russia and Fascist state in the 1930s and 1940s, broadcasting has been co-opted as a propaganda tool of authoritarian rule. In the UK radio and television broadcasting is conceived and born as utilities 'services to be developed as a national public interest' (Scannell and Cardiff, 1991, p. 8). Development in this form is preferred as the main reasons: the perception, among politicians, social scientists and intellectuals, that broadcasting is a unique and powerful medium. Too strong, in fact, to be placed in the hands of commercial interests. Overpowering, Also, to be left susceptible to political abuse. None of the parties in the British multiparty democracy want to allow the possibility of one of its competitors to gain control of broadcasting to pursue their own interests.

Thus, the British Broadcasting Corporation (BBC) came into being as a publicly-funded (from taxation, in the form of license fees), but independent political institution, is protected from interference in its activities by the government. Even when commercial principles are allowed to enter the arena of British broadcasting with the formation of the Independent Television network in 1954, laws were passed to prohibit the output experiencing political or economic pressure undue. Duopoly of public service in 1982, which consists of four channels (BBC1, BBC2, ITV and Channel 4) lasted until the late 1980s, when the development of cable and satellite technology, reinforced by the conservative government policies of deregulation of broadcasting began eroding.

Unlike the press, the British broadcasting has always been subject to close regulation, either by legal means and through regulatory bodies such as the Independent Television Commission and the Broadcasting Standards Commission. This institute oversees the performance of the broadcaster to ensure that the message delivered is consistent with the criteria of public services such as good taste, diversity, political neutrality and, relevant. 1990 Broadcasting Act requires broadcasters to observe 'impartiality in their coverage of the political issues, to ensure' adequate or appropriate, and the balance during the election campaign, (McNair, 2009b).

Democracy and The Media

Such as Nimmo and Combs said, 'History, the mass media were heralded as the main instrument of democracy. [The media] are destined to unite, educate, and, as a result, increase the actions and political decisions' (1992, p. Xv). Scannell and Cardiff observed that the role of the BBC, from the beginning, was to create "a public opinion and reasoning as an important part of the political process in a democratic mass society" (1991, p. 8). The role of media democracy will be met, if on the one hand, 'compliance with professional ethics of journalists to report the facts objectivity in public affairs. Objectivity is implied clearly distanced journalism of opinions expressed in the political debate, and the determination to not confuse the opinions of the Reports the facts. Opportunities to express their political opinions by journalists is very limited. The press, on the contrary, with a particular role in a free exchange or 'market' ideas, which are allowed, and indeed expected, to take a political position. They are 'partial', as opposed to the impartiality learned from the announcer. This means that even after the British press was left from a direct connection with party political organization in the nineteenth century (Negrine, 1993), each of the newspapers continue to have political views and express it in their content. That is the democratic principle has been maintained as far as newspapers and magazines reveals the plurality of opinions, according to various opinions circulating in the public space. The diversity of the party system is aligned in the press pluralism. The media in the twentieth century came to represent for most people, most of the time, the media as the main source of political information. Press and broadcasting become 'primary means of "mediation", ie, that stands between people and the world and reporting them what they can not see or experience' (Nimmo and Combs, 1983, p. 12). As Blumler Jay said, 'when the social confidence of public and political institutions has declined sharply. , , voters have become more dependent on media resource. for an impression of what is seen '(1987, p. 170). The media not only provides the

cognitive knowledge, informing them of what had happened, but they also order and the reality of the political structure, making the significance of events larger or smaller according to their presence or the presence of the media agenda. Indeed, the agenda-setting function of the media debated by many observers to be their main contribution to the political process (McCombs, 1981). As citizens, we can not understand or digest anything like the totality of events in the real world, and so we rely on the media to search and filter reality for the most important events. During the election campaign, for example, David Weaver show sufficient support for that mass media is very important in determining the public importance of the problem, at least the general issues outside the experience of most people '(1987, p. 186). Chapter 2 noted that the main purpose of political communication is to set the public agenda in a way that is favorable to the achievement of company objectives organization. The media, however, is the agenda-setters in their capacity as providers of information, highlighting some issues and ignore others, for reasons that are often beyond the capacity of politicians to influence significantly. Often in this manner, it is difficult to distinguish the agenda-setting media activities from those of politicians. A variation on the theme of agenda-setting, and one that looked at the media agency that works with political actors, presented by Greenaway et al, in their analysis of the factors involved in government. policy-making and implementation (1992). In the case of HIV / AIDS epidemic, they noted that the problem is largely absent from the political agenda until 1986 or thereabouts, at which point it began to receive extensive coverage in the media. As a result of this coverage, Miller et al argue, the government started for the first time to use the media as an educational tool of anti-HIV / AIDS (Miller et al., 1998). The media, in this sense, to put HIV / AIDS on the public agenda, Molotch et al. describes the relationship between media coverage and political decision making in terms of models' ecology ', based on' the need for a working model that includes not only a way of understanding how the public and policy actors establish an agenda and perspective, but what about the agenda of journalism was formed as well, and how the two sectors the establishment of inter-related realities '(1987, p. 28. They add that media effects are embedded in the policy actions of actors, such as policy actors' behavior that appears to be reflected in the formulation of journalists. Media and policies are part of a single ecological culture in which materials accumulate and disappear, often without realizing it, the whole web-media policy (Ibid.).

Some Feedback Media

To say that the media have an important cognitive effects and agenda-setting in a modern democracy possible, by this stage, the statement was clear. More contentious, however, is a benign view of the role of the media described in the previous section. Many observers have challenged the notion of liberal democracy 'public space' and the contribution of the media (Entman, 1989). For some, the very media output form militates against the understanding of the audience, while others feel the media as an ideological institution in a society where political power is not distributed in a fair or rational, but on the basis of class and economic status.

The first criticism voiced by Colin Sparks who noted the importance of culture media, in English and in a capitalist society more media focus on the issues 'are not usually associated with the public sphere, such as the sex scandal, human interest, and crime fiction weird' (1992, p. 22). The quality of journalism, in the words of one observer, generate the information necessary for the smooth public sphere and political parties of the government. It is common knowledge about policies - comprehensive social events and movements that are distanced from the materiality of everyday life '(Fiske, 1992, p. 49). On the contrary, argues Sparks, the popular press 'offers an immediate clear framework [of the social and political reality] in the event that causes the individual and personal and responses' (1992, p. 22). As said by critics, journalism be fundamentally apolitical. Josef Gripsund say, journalism push 'isolation, silence and non-participation in the political process (1992, p. 94), and is' part of the tendency to divert public attention from the principles of the problems with pseudo-insight offers voyeuristic individual affair. Here we note that even conservative argument Fiske, owned media as a result of the commercial position, a deep interest in maximizing the audience. To do this often involves their picture with a story that is totally meaningless. Fiske further, affirming that popular journalism is journalism that is more honest, less reactionary and more relevant to the world in which most people live on the 'quality' journalism is considered superior by the majority of liberal commentators. For Fiske, a collision between the commercial and popular rhetoric needs to create a space where a significant political criticism and disagreement can arise. The existence of this space is an independent mode of the 'official' politics a media organization. However, for other observers, the fact that the popular media, and newspapers in particular, does have a political allegiance, which is more important for the understanding of the function of their democracy than any recognition, no matter how generous, anti-establishment their content. They

already see that in a capitalist society like the UK, the press is allowed to have an opinion and are expected to express them. In a pluralist democracy, ideally, those opinions should reflect the structure of bias in society as a whole, serves diversity and promote rational debate, the common interests between the different viewpoints. Historically, most British newspapers have supported one party - the Conservative Party, which has a refractive pattern that peaked in the early 1990s. For this reason, Twenty-five general elections later evidence convincing impact on the voting behavior of the press are still not available. At least for now, and that newspaper readers want them to reflect the shift of loyalty editorial. When elite managed to mobilize consent, Gramsci calls them do hegemonic position, which means that there is no need to protect the social structure by coercion and force of arms, but citizens approve the system and their place in it. Maintenance hegemony, he argues, a cultural process, in which the media plays a big role. For Daniel Hallin, 'to say the media play the role of "hegemonic" saying that they contribute to the maintenance agreement for the power system' (1987, p. 18).

The emphasis here is not on the media support for a particular political party (bias or partiality in the narrow sense) but the part they play in strengthening and reproducing the popular general consensus on attaching the viability of the overall system. Gwynn Williams defines hegemony as the order in which a certain way to impose life and thought is dominant, in which one concept of reality spread throughout society in all institutional and manifestations private, informed by the spirit of all taste, morality, customs, religion and politics, and all social relations, especially in the intellectual and moral connotations. (Quoted in Miliband, 1973, p. 162) Ericson et al. shows that the hegemony of how to produce superordinates and maintain support for their domination of subordinates through the dissemination and reproduction of knowledge that supports their interests, and how alternative subordinates accept or contest their knowledge (1991, p 12). Reporters and their news organizations key players in the process of hegemonic. They not only report the incident, but participated in it and acts as a protagonist '(ibid., P. 16). The role of 'hegemonic media, as defined here, of course, can be regarded as completely benign, if someone chooses to accept the legitimacy of self ideology of capitalist society. From such a perspective it (what some might call the dominant ideological perspective) media provide a social structure with an outlet for the expression of shared values (as well as the political function of rational information discussed above). However, if one of the objects to the system, or part of it, the hegemonic role of cultural institutions such as the Media viewed negatively.

Ralph Miliband, the media in all capitalist societies consistently and largely has been a conservative institution indoctrination '(1973, p. 200). How these institutions realized? The broadcasters' The concept of impartiality, for example, is working to contain the political debate in a less tightly when pulled consensus, which recognizes only the political class is well established and often communication argues that, like other categories of output media, information about politics can have an effect only in a particular context, which shaped structure and audience response. A further objection to the effect of 'hipidemic' political tabloid journalism would be true if, as has been shown, the Labor Party in 1997 had the support of about 70 per cent of the national press circulation. The evidence assembled by Miller and others showing the relationship between the press and readers voting behavior are ambiguous and difficult to interpret, as in all aspects of media effects research.

Media and Hegemony

'The effects of the political media can be seen from term changes in behavior or attitude. In 1920 a Marxist intellectual Antonio Gramsci derived from the Italian political sociology has been concerned with how a perfect democracy with the consent and authority can be mobilized, in conditions of social inequality and distinctive even the most advanced capitalist societies. For the record Bobbio when stratified society of class, gender, ethnicity, age, level of education and democratic participation rates are substantially lower than the theory of liberal democracy. In political coverage, impartiality means giving equal representation to political parties, especially during election campaigns. Broadcast ban proposed by the conservative government of Ireland in 1989 and removed in 1994, when television and radio were prevented from broadcasting the voices of some Northern Ireland politicians elected because they are considered to support the legitimacy of the opponents of the British state. In this case, from the viewpoint of hegemonic media establish a barrier between the political discourse legitimate and illegitimate, including from public space.

The media also contribute to the maintenance agreements and policies. Third world liberation struggle being reported as 'communist aggression'; try to withstand the economic exploitation of the third world by US companies as a 'threat to US interests', and the brutal repression in East Timor, Chile and elsewhere as a legitimate activity and anti-subversive, if not ignored entirely.

In a press release, the structural dependence on official sources often allow the official view of winning. All these factors have been advanced as reasons for pro-systemic bias depth of the

media. Model hegemonic itself has been criticized, however, for it to be too simple to read about how politics to media reports.

David Murphy's analysis of how the media reported the incident at John Stalker also doubts against hegemonic models, arguing that the media in this regard actively promoting an anti-establishment conspiracy theories to explain the treatment of Stalker in Northern Ireland. In this case most of the cases the media arrived at a consensus that challenge the legitimacy of the state in its handling of the affair. Scope affairs Stalker expressed willingness on the part of journalists 'to question not only the wisdom of government policies or goodwill of individual politicians, but questioned the good faith and legitimacy of the State and its agencies, and the establishment of which is seen as lying behind them' (Ibid., P . 262). In reporting objectively real behavior of corrupt or unethical by the political class, will lead to fragmentation and division. The media contribute to the broader popular belief in rectifying nature of the system. They might do this, but they also do what journalists consider to be their professional duties, regardless of the political class.

Liberal journalism has evolved over three centuries or more as autonomous political and cultural power, strength and prestige is measured at least in part by the readiness of journalists to serve as the fourth pillar, look out for and expose abuses of political power. Most important emerging political scope of application of the hegemonic professional. Ethics for the media should be able to accommodate the frequent examples of damage 'of the consensus and the separation of the elite group. In the second perspective, the adaptation of media to shift the debate is very important line for the retention of their legitimacy as a facilitator of the political discourse in the public sphere and therefore, ultimately, for the 'hegemonic' their role.

Politics and Media Production

Many types of media output in the preceding section can be more easily understood by an analysis of the media production process conventions, practices and constraints that shape political outputs journalism, in a way that sometimes supportive politicians, and on the other hand sometimes dropped. These can be grouped into three categories: commercial, organizational and professional.

Commercial

In the commercial constraints Greg Philo noted that 'the truth underlying the simple practice of media institutions and journalists who work in them - that they are all in competition

with each other to sell the story and maximizing audience. They should do this with certain costs and the level of resources' (1993a, p. 111). The main purpose of the press, mass media since its emergence in the nineteenth century, has produced information in the form of commodities, and to maximize ad revenue by selling the information to the readership. On the other side of broadcasting, relatively short existence, have been accommodated in many countries of commercialism. In the British BBC, defined from the beginning as a 'public service' and given noble cause of cultural enlightenment and education. While commercial organizations ITV also revenue comes from advertising, which is required by law to broadcast most of the news and current affairs programming, and to create programs within the same rules that guided the BBC's impartiality. In general, journalism has proven to be popular and profitable, and there is no evidence that the commercialization of British broadcasting, as some analysts feared in the late 1980s, accompanied with the exception of the airways. When a story is considered to have become "news" by one organization, others feel compelled to follow. This is not necessarily because the story had a 'goal' is important, but often will be the product of editorial assumption that to be left to the commercial organization of the position and legitimacy as a news provider. In the competitive environment intensifies, therefore the political process came to be seen by journalists as raw material commodity news or current affairs - which eventually have to be sold with the maximum number of consumers. What is important (political talk) and entertaining are not mutually exclusive. In many cases, when commercial considerations drive both the print and broadcast media, the commercialization of the media for some reason seen by politicians as a threat to traditional loyalties and alliances.

Organization Needs to News

While commercialization of the media may have some unintended consequences for the political class, the trend is promising enough other related benefits. Part of the increased competitive pressures in which the broadcaster is a consequence of the expansion of the media is made possible by cable, satellite and digital technology. All this means that there is an increasing demand for news material, to serve politicians. For the news-hungry media, the political arena is a potential source of an endless stream of stories, some of them are not desirable for politicians, as we have seen, but others pulled in so far as they provide publicity and promotion for the party, government or leader. This source is becoming more important due to increased demand news.

Thus developed a symbiotic relationship between politicians and journalists, each of which can be more profitable (Blumler and Gurevitch, 1981).

Rodney Tiffen observed that "news is a parasitic institution. It depends on the public information activities of other agencies" (1989, p. 51). One of the researchers write coverage of political affairs in Germany that about two out of every three [news] items, on the basis of the main sources respectively. the outcome of press releases and conferences, while the rest can be traced back to public events, investigative journalism, or non-public events that journalists were invited. Hence, the formation of the reality presented by the news media that may, on the basis of empirical evidence, attributed mainly to the sector, and not autonomous activities of journalists. (Baerns, 1987, p. 101). While some observers have complained about what they see as critical media, non-discriminatory use of PR (Bagdikian, 1984; Michie, 1998), for political actors in such circumstances there is much to be gained by learning how to work the media - news value, professional practices and routines - and use this knowledge to journalists with information in the way most likely to be accepted and turned into news. As Tiffen notes, news production 'generates a pattern [Journalism] response of political leaders [and political actors in] public can utilize' (1989, p. 74). Skilled politicians have been manipulating the media in this mode for the decade 1962, as Daniel Boorstin's discussion of pseudo-events make it clear, but certainly there is a greater opportunity to do so in an era when news space to be filled has grown dramatically. The astute politician would know, for example, that in a situation where media organizations have limited resources of time and money, tight deadlines and exclusive increasingly important, there is much to be gained by ensuring ease of supply of journalists, providing as an 'information subsidies' (1994). A media event was time to meet the deadline for the first edition or a prime-time news bulletins will have more possibilities were reported. Problems that can be packed neatly and told in a relatively simple, dramatic terms would receive more coverage than complex. Media production process is one that can be studied, understood and manipulated by those who want to get access to lucrative. Political actors with the largest resource base to pursue a strategy of this kind is located in the established institutions of power, such as government and state organizations. They have the most money that can be used to employ the best news, managers set the grandest events and produce a press release.

Conclusion

Another element of the media production process which can be said to support the establishment is professional ethics of objectivity itself (and its close relation, impartiality) that the majority of political reporters. Objectivity is an important democratic process because it allows the media to report on political events is accurate, fair and independent. Concretely, the ethics of objectivity has gradually developed into a set of practices and conventions that indicates, when present in journalism, was intended to secure the support of the audience 'truth' it. These practices include explicit separation of fact from opinion, which is included in a range opposite sides in the debate (not including, typically, terrorists and other non-constitutional actors), and validation of journalistic narrative by citations from reliable, authoritative source. Fair to say that for most journalists, most reliable and authoritative when establishing their political story is the senior politicians were civil servants and secretaries, and other figures in the State and the public. Professional requirements of objectivity thus amplified by technical obstacles in the process of news gathering.

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